

Qasr al-Bint

Secondary source

Entered by Daniel Plekhov, Brown University

* Secondary Source entry, prepared from a literature review by a Ph.D. RA

Entry tags: Religious Place, Temple, Altar, Religious Group, Levantine Religion, Arabian Religions

The Qasr al-Bint is a free-standing temple structure built at Petra by the Nabataeans, likely sometime around the first century BCE. The structure is one of the most prominent and centrally located at Petra, standing at the western end of the main colonnaded street and nearby to other notable buildings, such as the Great Temple. Even so, the Qasr al-Bint is structurally set apart from these other buildings, both in terms of its unique alignment as well as by a temenos enclosure and gate structure that separates it from the rest of Petra's city center. Within this sanctuary enclosure are other associated structures, most notably an altar directly across from the entrance to the Qasr al-Bint. This altar was dedicated to the principal Nabataean deity Dushara, and it has been proposed that the Qasr al-Bint itself was also dedicated to this deity (alternatives include Al-Uzza/Aphrodite). With the Roman annexation of the Nabataean kingdom in 106 CE, remodeling took place of much of Petra's principal monuments, including the Qasr al-Bint, and it is possible that the temple was rededicated to other deities at this time. Little else is known about the use or functions of the Qasr al-Bint during the Nabataean and Roman periods. Given its prominent location and size, it likely functioned as one of the principal religious structures of Petra and the Nabataeans, but little else can be said about what kinds of rituals or activities took place at the temple, who participated in them, or how frequently they occurred. We do not even know what name the temple originally had. The modern Arabic name today is translated as "the palace of (Pharaoh's) daughter," in reference to local folklore. By the third century CE, the structure seems to have been largely abandoned and in disrepair, perhaps as a result of earthquakes, the Palmyrene revolt, or general lack of maintenance.

Date Range: 30 BCE - 400 CE

Region: Qasr al-Bint

Region tags: Asia, Western Asia, Jordan

Extent and location of the Qasr al-Bint

Status of Participants:

✓ Elite ✓ Religious Specialists ✓ Non-elite (common people, general populace)

General Variables

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

— Source 1: Shenwan Al-Bashaireh, Khaled; W.L Hodgins, Gregory (2014). "The Chronology of Qasr el-Bint, Petra: Discussion and New Radiocarbon Dates". *Palestine Exploration Quarterly*. 146: 281-292.

Reference: Augé, Christian, Laurent Borel, Jacqueline Dentzer-Feydy, Chrystelle March, François Renel, and Laurent Tholbecq. "Le Sanctuaire Du Qasr Al-bint Et Ses Abords". *Syria* 93 (2016): 255-310.
<https://doi.org/10.4000/syria.4689>.

Reference: Mouton, Michel, Francois Renel, and Andreas Kropp. "The Hellenistic Levels Under the

Temenos of the Qasr Al-bint at Petra". Annual of the Department of Antiquities of Jordan 52 (2008): 51-71.

Reference: Renel, François. "L'abandon Du Secteur Du Qasr Al-bint À Pétra: Nouveaux Éléments Archéologiques". In *Studies in the History and Archaeology of Jordan*, 348-58. edited by Fares al-Hmoud. Amman: Department of Antiquities, 2013.

Reference: Renel, François, and Michel Mouton. "The Architectural Remains and Pottery Assemblage from the Early Phases at the Qasr Al-bint". In *Men on the Rocks: The Formation of Nabataean Petra*, edited by Stephan G. Schmid, 57-78. Berlin: logos, 2013.

Reference: Zayadine, Fawzi, François Larché, and Jacqueline Dentzer-Feydy. *Le Qasr Al-bint De Pétra: L'architecture, Le Décor, La Chronologie Et Les Dieux*. Paris: Recherche sur les civilisations, 2003.

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

↳ A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape

– Rectangular

↳ One single feature

– Water channel

↳ A group of structures:

– I don't know

↳ A group of features:

– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:

– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:

– I don't know

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:

Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function

– Worship

↳ Worship:

– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:

– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:

– Yes

Reference: Dentzer-Feydy, Jacqueline. "The Sanctuary of the Qasr Al-bint in Petra: From Nabataean Cult to Roman Imperial Celebration". In *Contextualizing the Sacred in the Hellenistic and Roman Near East*, n.d..

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:

– I don't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:

– Yes

Reference: Al-Saada, Ziad, and Mohamed A.H Abdel-Halim. "Laboratory Evaluation of Various Types of Mortars for the Conservation of Qasr Al-bint Monument, Petra-jordan". *Engineering Structure* 23, no. 8 (2001): 926–33. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296\(00\)00115-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296(00)00115-2).

Reference: Bani-Hani, Khaldoon, and Samer Barakat. "Analytical Evaluation of Repair and Strengthening Measures of Qasr Al-bint Historical Monument–petra, Jordan". *Engineering Structures* 28, no. 10 (n.d.).

↳ In antiquity

– More than once

↳ In modernity

– Post-Renaissance

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:

– Yes

|

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:

–Yes [specify]: Dushara

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:

–Yes [specify]: Aphrodite, perhaps

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

↳ Type of feature

–Water feature

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:

– I don't know

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qasr_al-Bint

– Source 1 Description: Wikipedia entry

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

↳ Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:

– I don't know

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

↳ Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Reference: Graf, David Frank, Stephan G. Schmid, and Elena Ronza. "The Hellenistic Petra Project: Excavations in the Qaşr Al-bint Temenos Area: Preliminary Report of the Second Season, 2005". *Annual of the Department of Antiquities of Jordan* 51 (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210854>.

Reference: Kanellopoulos, Chrysanthos. "A New Plan of Petra's City Center". *Near Eastern Archaeology* 65, no. 4 (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210854>.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

–Other [specify]: Field does not know

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Sources and Excavations

Print Sources

Print sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1: Shenwan Al-Bashaireh, Khaled; W.L Hodgins, Gregory (2014). "The Chronology of Qasr el-Bint, Petra: Discussion and New Radiocarbon Dates". *Palestine Exploration Quarterly*. 146: 281-292.

Reference: Augé, Christian, Laurent Borel, Jacqueline Dentzer-Feydy, Chrystelle March, François Renel, and Laurent Tholbecq. "Le Sanctuaire Du Qasr Al-bint Et Ses Abords". *Syria* 93 (2016): 255-310. <https://doi.org/10.4000/syria.4689>.

Reference: Mouton, Michel, Francois Renel, and Andreas Kropp. "The Hellenistic Levels Under the Temenos of the Qasr Al-bint at Petra". *Annual of the Department of Antiquities of Jordan* 52 (2008): 51-71.

Reference: Renel, François. "L'abandon Du Secteur Du Qasr Al-bint À Pétra: Nouveaux Éléments Archéologiques". In *Studies in the History and Archaeology of Jordan*, 348-58. edited by Fares al-Hmoud. Amman: Department of Antiquities, 2013.

Reference: Renel, François, and Michel Mouton. "The Architectural Remains and Pottery Assemblage from the Early Phases at the Qasr Al-bint". In *Men on the Rocks: The Formation of Nabataean Petra*, edited by Stephan G. Schmid, 57-78. Berlin: logos, 2013.

Reference: Zayadine, Fawzi, François Larché, and Jacqueline Dentzer-Feydy. *Le Qasr Al-bint De Pétra: L'architecture, Le Décor, La Chronologie Et Les Dieux*. Paris: Recherche sur les civilisations, 2003.

Online Sources

Online sources used for understanding this subject:

– Source 1 URL: https://en.wikipedia.org/wiki/Qasr_al-Bint

– Source 1 Description: Wikipedia entry

Has this place been the focus of excavation (pre-modern, illicit, or scientific):

Answer 'Yes' for each period or type of excavation.

– Yes

Type of excavation:

– Scientific

Topographical Context

Does the place involve human-made features besides structure:

Other features might be ground clearing, terracing, other modifications of the local environment.

– Yes

Type of feature

– Water feature

Is the place situated in an urban or significantly urbanized area:

– Yes

Is there a distinct boundary between the place and the urban fabric:

– Yes

Reference: Graf, David Frank, Stephan G. Schmid, and Elena Ronza. "The Hellenistic Petra Project: Excavations in the Qaşr Al-bint Temenos Area: Preliminary Report of the Second Season, 2005". *Annual of the Department of Antiquities of Jordan* 51 (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210854>.

Reference: Kanellopoulos, Chrysanthos. "A New Plan of Petra's City Center". *Near Eastern Archaeology* 65, no. 4 (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210854>.

Is the place located significantly within the urban fabric:

Is the place centrally located, or at the crossroads of significant pathways?

– Yes

Is the place situated in a rural setting:

– No

Is the place situated far removed from non-religious places of habitation:

– No

Structures Present

Are there structures or features present:

Instructions: Answer for each structure/feature or group that can be differentiated.

– Yes

A single structure

– Yes

↳ The structure has a definite shape
– Rectangular

↳ One single feature
– Water channel

↳ A group of structures:
– I don't know

↳ A group of features:
– Yes

↳ Are they part of a single design/construction stage:
– Yes

↳ Is it part of a larger place/sanctuary:
– I don't know

↳ What is the function of the structure/feature or group:
Answer "Yes" once for each distinct function
– Worship

↳ Worship:
– Communal

↳ Is the structure/feature finished:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature intended to last beyond a generation:
– Yes

↳ Was the structure/feature modified through time:
– Yes

Reference: Dentzer-Feydy, Jacqueline. "The Sanctuary of the Qasr Al-bint in Petra: From

Nabataean Cult to Roman Imperial Celebration". In Contextualizing the Sacred in the Hellenistic and Roman Near East, n.d..

↳ Was the structure/feature destroyed:
– I don't know

↳ Has the structure/feature been reconstructed:
– Yes

Reference: Al-Saada, Ziad, and Mohamed A.H Abdel-Halim. "Laboratory Evaluation of Various Types of Mortars for the Conservation of Qasr Al-bint Monument, Petra-jordan". *Engineering Structure* 23, no. 8 (2001): 926–33. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296\(00\)00115-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296(00)00115-2).

Reference: Bani-Hani, Khaldoon, and Samer Barakat. "Analytical Evaluation of Repair and Strengthening Measures of Qasr Al-bint Historical Monument—petra, Jordan". *Engineering Structures* 28, no. 10 (n.d.).

↳ In antiquity
– More than once

↳ In modernity
– Post-Renaissance

Reasons for Creation/Construction/Consecration

Is the place used for the worship of/communication with non-human supernatural beings:
– Yes

↳ Dedicated to a supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Dushara

↳ Dedicated to more than one supernatural being:
– Yes [specify]: Aphrodite, perhaps

Is the place used for the worship of a semi-divine human being:
– I don't know

Is the place used for the worship of non-divine ancestors:
– I don't know

Was the place commissioned/built by an official political entity:

A political entity is a local power structure that leverages a workforce.

– I don't know

Were the Structures built by specific groups of people:

– I don't know

Was the place thought to have originated as the result of divine intervention:

– I don't know

Was the place created to mark or commemorate the birthplace of a supernatural or human being:

– Field doesn't know

Was the place created as the result of an event:

– Field doesn't know

Was the creation of the place sponsored by external financial/material donation:

– Field doesn't know

Was the establishment of the place motivated by:

– Other [specify]: Field does not know

Was the place built specifically for housing scriptures/sacred texts:

– Field doesn't know

Design and Material Remains

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:

– I don't know

Is decoration present:

– I don't know

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– I don't know

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 140

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 23

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:
– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:
– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass

– I don't know

↳ Stone

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials

– I don't know

Overall Structure

Is the place made up of multiple built structures:

– Yes

↳ Are any of the structures attached to or associated with a landscape feature:
– I don't know

↳ Are any of the structures attached to other structures:
– Yes

↳ Is there a hierarchy among the structures:
– Yes

Is monumental architecture present:

Monumental architecture is defined here as a built structure that surpasses average human proportions and in general is larger and more complex than is necessary to fulfill the structure's utilitarian function(s). Examples of monumental architecture include Mesopotamian Ziggurats, Egyptian Pyramids, Greek and Roman temples, Mesoamerican Pyramids, North American and Aegean burial mounds, etc.

– Yes

↳ In the average place, what percentage of area is taken up by built monuments:
– I don't know

↳ Footprint of largest single religious monument, square meters:
Please add dimensions in the comments, if known.
– Square meters: 140

↳ Height of largest single religious monument, meters:
– Height, meters: 23

↳ Size of average monument, square meters:

– I don't know

↳ Height of average monument, meters:

– I don't know

Is the structure/feature made out of natural materials:

Answer [Yes] for each material type

– Yes

↳ Earth

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Sand

– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:

– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:

– No

↳ Clay

– I don't know

↳ Plaster

– I don't know

↳ Wood

– I don't know

↳ Grass
– I don't know

↳ Stone
– Yes

↳ Is this material sourced locally:
– Yes

↳ Is this material lacking in the local natural environment:
– No

Is the structure/feature made out of human-made materials
– I don't know

Decoration

Is decoration present:
– I don't know

Iconography

Are there distinct features in the places iconography:
– I don't know

Beliefs and Practices

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:

– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:

– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:

– Field doesn't know

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

↳ Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: There is a main altar, but it is unclear what would have been sacrificed.

↳ Are there human sacrifices:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:

– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:

– Yes

↳ Are they cthonic (underworld)

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)

– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:

– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:

– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other:

–Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicates with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are nonhuman supernatural beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Are formal burials present:

– No

Are mixed human-divine beings are present:

– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):

– I don't know

Funerary Associations

Is this place a tomb/burial:

– No

Is this a place for the worship of the dead:

– Field doesn't know

Is this a place for treatment of the corpse:

– Field doesn't know

Are co-sacrifices present in tomb/burial:

Co-sacrifices are animal/human sacrifices prompted by the death of the primary occupant of the tomb/burial.

– No

Are grave goods present:

– No

Are formal burials present:

– No

Supernatural Beings

Is a supreme high god is present:

– Yes

↳ Are they anthropomorphic:
– Yes

↳ Are they sky deity:
– Yes

↳ Are they cthonoic (underworld)
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they fused with king/kingship role (king = high god)
– Yes

↳ Are they the monarch is seen as a manifestation or emanation of the high god:
– Yes

↳ Are they kin relation to elites:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other type of loyalty or connection to elites:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they unquestionably good:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are they other:
– Other [specify]: Field doesn't know

Does the supreme high god communicates with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are previously human spirits present:
– Field doesn't know

Do human spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are nonhuman supernatural beings are present:
– Field doesn't know

Do nonhuman spirits communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Are mixed human-divine beings are present:
– Field doesn't know

Do mixed human-divine beings communicate with the living at this place:
– Field doesn't know

Is the supernatural being/high god present in the form of a cult statue(s):
– I don't know

Supernatural Interactions

Is supernatural monitoring present:

– Field doesn't know

Do visitors communicate with the gods or supernatural beings:

– Field doesn't know

Ritual and Performance

Do rituals occur at this place:

Rituals are visibly enacted behaviors by one or more people for the purposes of religious observance.

– Yes

↳ Do large-scale rituals take place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Do small-scale rituals take place:
– Field doesn't know

↳ On average how many participants are present in large-scale rituals:
– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ How often do these rituals take place:
– specify: Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthodoxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there orthopraxy checks:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there synchronic practices:
– Field doesn't know

↳ Are there intoxicants used during the ritual:
– Field doesn't know

Sacrifices, Offerings, and Maintenance

Are sacrifices performed at this place:

– Yes

Are there animal sacrifices:

– Yes [specify]: There is a main altar, but it is unclear what would have been sacrificed.

Are there human sacrifices:

– Field doesn't know

Are the sacrificed humans associated in some way:

– Field doesn't know

Are there self-sacrifices present:

– Field doesn't know

Are material offerings present:

– I don't know

Is attendance to worship/sacrifice mandatory:

– Field doesn't know

Is maintenance of the place performed:

– I don't know

Pilgrimage and Festivals

Are pilgrimages present:

– Field doesn't know

Is this place a venue for feasting:

– No

Are festivals present:

– Field doesn't know

Divination and Healing

Is divination present:

– I don't know

Is healing present/practiced at this place:

– Field doesn't know

Institutions and Scriptures

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintenance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals whose primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintenance of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place

– Field doesn't know

Is this place used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Field doesn't know

Religious Specialists

Are religious specialists present/in charge of this place:

Religious specialists are individuals who's primary duties within a population group are not concerned with subsistence or craft production but the maintaince of the religious landscape and culture of the group.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place incorporate a living space for religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Is this palce used for the training of religious specialists:

– Field doesn't know

Are there formal institutions for the maintenance of the place:
institutions that are authorized by the religious community or political leaders
– Field doesn't know

Bureaucracy

Is there a formal bureaucracy present at this place:

A bureaucracy consists of a hierarchical system of accounting and rule maintance primarily concerned with material wealth.

– Field doesn't know

Does this place control economic resources (land, goods, tools):

– Field doesn't know

Public Works

Does this place serve as a location for services to the community:

– Field doesn't know

Writing/Scriptures

Is non-religious writing stored at this place:

Economic documents, records etc.

– Field doesn't know

Are there scriptures associated with this place

– Field doesn't know

Bibliography

Entry/Answer References

Reference: Source 1: Shenwan Al-Bashaireh, Khaled; W.L Hodgins, Gregory (2014). "The Chronology of Qasr el-Bint, Petra: Discussion and New Radiocarbon Dates". *Palestine Exploration Quarterly*. 146: 281-292., Augé, Christian, Laurent Borel, Jacqueline Dentzer-Feydy, Chrystelle March, François Renel, and Laurent Tholbecq. "Le Sanctuaire Du Qasr Al-bint Et Ses Abords". *Syria* 93 (2016): 255-310. <https://doi.org/10.4000/syria.4689>.

Reference: Source 1: Shenwan Al-Bashaireh, Khaled; W.L Hodgins, Gregory (2014). "The Chronology of Qasr el-Bint, Petra: Discussion and New Radiocarbon Dates". *Palestine Exploration Quarterly*. 146: 281-292., Mouton, Michel, Francois Renel, and Andreas Kropp. "The Hellenistic Levels Under the Temenos of the Qasr Al-bint at Petra". *Annual of the Department of Antiquities of Jordan* 52 (2008): 51-71.

Reference: Source 1: Shenwan Al-Bashaireh, Khaled; W.L Hodgins, Gregory (2014). "The Chronology of Qasr el-Bint, Petra: Discussion and New Radiocarbon Dates". *Palestine Exploration Quarterly*. 146: 281-292., Renel, François. "L'abandon Du Secteur Du Qasr Al-bint À Pétra: Nouveaux Éléments Archéologiques". In *Studies in the History and Archaeology of Jordan*, 348-58. edited by Fares al-Hmoud. Amman: Department of Antiquities, 2013.

Reference: Source 1: Shenwan Al-Bashaireh, Khaled; W.L Hodgins, Gregory (2014). "The Chronology of Qasr el-Bint, Petra: Discussion and New Radiocarbon Dates". *Palestine Exploration Quarterly*. 146: 281-292., Renel, François, and Michel Mouton. "The Architectural Remains and Pottery Assemblage from the Early Phases at the Qasr Al-bint". In *Men on the Rocks: The Formation of Nabataean Petra*, edited by Stephan G. Schmid, 57-78. Berlin: logos, 2013.

Reference: Source 1: Shenwan Al-Bashaireh, Khaled; W.L Hodgins, Gregory (2014). "The Chronology of Qasr el-Bint, Petra: Discussion and New Radiocarbon Dates". *Palestine Exploration Quarterly*. 146: 281-292., Zayadine, Fawzi, François Larché, and Jacqueline Dentzer-Feydy. *Le Qasr Al-bint De Pétra: L'architecture, Le Décor, La Chronologie Et Les Dieux*. Paris: Recherche sur les civilisations, 2003.

Reference: Yes, Graf, David Frank, Stephan G. Schmid, and Elena Ronza. "The Hellenistic Petra Project: Excavations in the Qasr Al-bint Temenos Area: Preliminary Report of the Second Season, 2005". *Annual of the Department of Antiquities of Jordan* 51 (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210854>.

Reference: Yes, Kanellopoulos, Chrysanthos. "A New Plan of Petra's City Center". *Near Eastern Archaeology* 65, no. 4 (n.d.). <https://doi.org/10.2307/3210854>.

Reference: Yes, Dentzer-Feydy, Jacqueline. "The Sanctuary of the Qasr Al-bint in Petra: From Nabataean Cult to Roman Imperial Celebration". In *Contextualizing the Sacred in the Hellenistic and Roman Near East*, n.d..

Reference: Yes, Al-Saada, Ziad, and Mohamed A.H Abdel-Halim. "Laboratory Evaluation of Various Types of Mortars for the Conservation of Qasr Al-bint Monument, Petra-jordan". *Engineering Structure* 23, no. 8 (2001): 926–33. [https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296\(00\)00115-2](https://doi.org/10.1016/S0141-0296(00)00115-2).

Reference: Yes, Bani-Hani, Khaldoon, and Samer Barakat. "Analytical Evaluation of Repair and Strengthening Measures of Qasr Al-bint Historical Monument—petra, Jordan". *Engineering Structures* 28, no. 10 (n.d.).